

DEVELOPMENT AND ACHIEVEMENT OF POMEGRANATE INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya: *This article provides information on the widespread use of pomegranate in Uzbekistan today, as well as measures taken to select and adapt to the climatic conditions of pomegranate varieties and their achievements. We can also learn about our pomegranate regions and their export potential.*

Keywords: *pomegranate, ecological, plantations, export, pharmaceutical industries.*

In recent years, the country has been paying great attention to the optimization of arable land, the placement of agricultural crops based on soil and climatic conditions. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29. 2015 “On measures for further reform and development of agroculture in 2020” In order to release cotton and use the these lands more efficiently, the cultivation of appropriate agricultural crops is planned for the fall.

Today, the emergence of forms suitable for a market economy, the preservation of existing lands, increasing its productivity and economic efficiency, in particular, linking economic sectors, including agriculture, with the growth rate of the population, in based on a science-based system and other happened.

In this regard, the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, developed on the initiative of **President Shavkat Mirziyoyev** on the basis of current legislation, law enforcement and analysis of the best international practice, is also important.

In this years, Uzbekistan has been paying special attention to pomegranate cultivation. In the near future, the country's annual production is projected to exceed at least 600,000 tons. Also, in 2026, the demand for pomegranate products in the global market may reach \$ 23.14 billion.

During the visit of President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev to Syrdarya region on May 17.2017, the resolution of the the enlarged meeting set separate tasks for the development of pomegranate growing in Syrdarya region and the cultivation of suitable and resistant plants for saline soils, serving as. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “ On measures for more efficient use of agricultural lands in Syrdarya region“

№ 690 of 2019 a number of works on cultivation have been carried out. In particular, pomegranate cultivation and processing has been launched in the region.

The trend of large-scale pomegranate cultivation in Uzbekistan is undoubtedly very interesting. But the prospect of this business will depend on the decisions made by the producers and the discussion of the level of cultivation and processing technologies of the products. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev during his visit to Fergana region on June 12-13. 2018, put forward many noble initiatives for the future in the process of creative work, acquaintance with major projects and dialogue with the people. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “ On measures to increase pomegranate cultivation and development of the industry in Fergana region “ October 4. **2018 № 791**. Assistance to private sector representatives, conducting research in cooperation with research institutes, cultivation of pomegranate seedlings and products on the basis of innovative resource-saving technologies, integrated development of its processing, further increasing the export potential of the industry and employment and income special attention is paid to raising the level.

Emphasis added it is worth noting that agrofirma the Fergana Pomegranate School has been established under the **Fergana Pomegranate School**. In collaboration with professors and specialists of Fergana State University, practical seminars were organized here for beginners in the field, and specialists of Fergana Pomegranate Agrofirma conducted exemplary construction of anoraks. It is ensured that each process of carrying out this work within the framework of quality, defined agro-technical measures is organized by combining life and scientific experience.

In 2018, it is planned to establish pomegranate orchards on 300 hectares of land in Rishtan district of Fergana region, for which 649.7 million soums were spent, about 250.000 pomegranate seedlings were planted and application were received from 40 project initiators, they were allotted plots of land. In turn, contracts were signing with 21 project initiators in the prescribed manner.

Especially the pomegranates of Sherabad are large, taste, fruitful. As a result, its market is booming and its popularity has spread abroad. This is a great opportunity for entrepreneurs, a source of income for the population 33 out of 48 neighborhoods is the district specialize in pomegranate cultivation. One of such pomegranates was established by “**Sardorbek Sultanbek**” Limited Liability Company in Boston neighborhood of the district and more than 30.000 pomegranates were planted on 43 hectares. One pomegranate of the Kazakh variety can weight more than 1 kilogram. Seedlings came into harvest this year. It is planning to produce more than a thousand tons of products a year.

It is expanding was announced that the total area of in Uzbekistan. It pomegranate orchards in Fergana region will be increased to 20.000 hectares by 2025 and more than 200.000 tons will be harvested annually. In particular, new pomegranate orchards have

been created on 1,400 hectares in Rishtan and Oltiariq district. The Ministry of Agriculture also announced that pomegranate plantations in Kashkadarya have increased by another 2,000 hectares. Taking into account the plans well as in Surkhandarya region and Fergana, as existing plantations in other regions of the country, the annual volume of pomegranate production in the country is expected to exceed at least 600,000 tons in the next 5-10 years.

If production grows so fast and traditional local varieties continue to be grown, it would be wise for Uzbekistan to consider industrial processing of pomegranates.

Pomegranates not only a market for fresh fruits, but also an interesting and useful fruit for the processing, food, cosmetics and even pharmaceutical industries. In the first 11 month of 2021, Uzbekistan sent 16.3 million US dollars to 16 foreign countries. It exported 16.1 thousand tons of pomegranates worth USD 1 billion. This was reported by the Statistics Committee.

Pomegranate export increased by 1.2 thousand tons compared to the corresponding period of 2020.

UZBEKISTAN is the largest exporter of pomegranates:

- **Russia- 6 thousand tons**
- **Kazakhstan- 5.6 thousand tons**
- **Krgyzstan- 2.1 thousand**
- **Tajikistan- 1.2 thousand**
- **Ukraine- 477 tons**

The regions that exported the most pomegranates were:

1. **Fergana region- 5.5 thousand tons**
2. **Surkhandarya region- 3.1 thousand tons**
3. **Tashkent region- 2.1 thousand tons**
4. **Khorezm region- 1.3 thousand tons**

By 2025, the area of pomegranates in the region will reach 20.000 hectares and more than 200.000 tons of pomegranates will be grown annually. This will allow to export more than 120 thousand tons of pomegranates during the season.

Conclusion: Today, the use of plant biotechnology methods in the creation of new varieties of plants or the selection of and varieties allows to substantiate a high degree of scientific significance of the recommended for production. Meeting the food needs of the population of your country, as well as maintaining and improving the health of the population is a constant and key task. The properties of the fruit of the pomegranate plant are that is strengthens the human immunity, strengthens the body`s fight against various infections and viruses, gives a person health and beauty, strength and freshness. In particular, it is noteworthy that pomegranate can prevent cancer and cardiovascular disease. Therefore it is necessary to increase the amount of pomegranate cultivation.

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